

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF BOLTED CERAMIC-MATRIX COMPOSITE JOINTS USING MULTI-INSTRUMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

This experimental study focuses on the analysis of the mechanical behaviour of a bolted joint composed of two ceramic composite plates. A single lap joint configuration was investigated under loading in tensile shearing. Two different set-ups were considered to analyse the impact of boundary conditions on mechanical behaviour of the assembly. A multi-instrumented approach consisting of digital image correlation and acoustic emission was used to characterize the whole damage process. The stereo digital image correlation allowed to measure strain and global displacement fields located on both the face and the side of the overlap area of the sample. Acoustic emission permitted to localize events registered during loading. An acoustic clustering approach was also suggested. Experimental results led to a good agreement and proved that coupling method is an interesting way to investigate the damage process at multiple scales.

1 INTRODUCTION

Ceramic matrix composite materials (CMC) are able to operate under oxidizing conditions at very high temperature and withstand high loads, which meets the requirements of the aircraft industry particularly in the engines hot sections. In this activity sector, such structural parts are required to be fastened by means of bolted joints.

A large number of studies deal with the mechanical behaviour and damage model of bolted joints, but most of them focused on metallic [1] or polymer matrix composite plates [2]. Only few research studies have been devoted to assemblies of CMC, which are materials having multiple damage mechanisms and thus a specific behaviour. In their studies [3-4], Li *et al.* mainly investigated parameters linked to the hole (number, diameter, edge distance). They pointed out an influence of assembly on fracture modes and properties. Global mechanical behaviour was not mentioned.

The main purpose of this experimental study is to identify the chronology of events occurring during damage process of a CMC single lap joint. The configuration was investigated under loading in tensile shearing.

The damage threshold in terms of strain on this type of material is very low. Only a specific and adjusted instrumentation allows to understand the material behaviour and determine damage threshold. The instrumentation used in the present work was based on previous studies by Tableau *et al.* [5-6]. These experimental technics allowed to characterize precisely the behaviour of 3D woven CMC plates during tensile and torsional tests.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Experimental design

Single lap joint configurations were tested under tensile loading at room temperature. The studied samples were produced and provided by Herakles from Safran Group. These assemblies were composed of two 3D woven reinforcement ceramic matrix composite plates. The plates were fastened by a bolted joint.

Two different set-ups were investigated for this experimental study. For the first set-up, the sample was fastened by two fixed clamping jaws preventing any movement, whereas in the other case, one of the clamping jaws was swivelled, thus allowing some degree of freedom. In order to distinguish the two types of configurations in the following of this article, the set-up with two fixed clamping jaws is referred to as “no swivelled clamp”, and the other set-up with one swivelled and one fixed clamping jaws is referred to as “with swivelled clamp”. A loading/unloading cycle was imposed on the specimen only for the latter set-up. In both cases, the tests were performed until rupture based on a prescribed displacement control.

As illustrated on figure 1, plate on the side of the bolt head was linked to the moving horizontal part of the test machine. This plate referred to as the “moving part”. The plate on the back of the sample was clamped to the frame. This part of the assembly referred to as the “fixed part”.

Figure 1: Separate analysis of the “fixed” and “moving” parts.

In order to characterize the behaviour and identify the nature of damage induced by the 3D architecture of the CMC weaving, the tests were monitored by two different experimental tools: stereo digital image correlation and acoustic emission (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Devices used for experimental study

2.2 Stereo digital image correlation

The face and the side of the overlap area of the samples were painted with a black and white speckle in order to make the digital image correlation (DIC) possible. The bolt head was also speckled.

A double stereo-DIC system was used to measure displacement and strain fields of the assembly during the test. The first system was focused on the side of the sample and the second one on the face.

The two CMC plates constituting the specimen (*i.e.* the “moving” and “fixed” parts) are investigated, and only areas on the overlap are studied. The displacement gap is computed as the difference between the mean displacements of the “moving” and “fixed” parts.

On the side of the sample, 80% of the overlap is considered. The longitudinal mean displacements of the fixed part” and “moving part”, as well as the displacement gap between the two parts, are deduced from this DIC system focused on the side. The values of the displacements are obtained by meaning the analysed area for each part.

57% of the overlap on the face is taken into account for processing due to the presence of AE sensors. Moreover on the face of the sample, the bolt head and the CMC “moving part” are separately investigated. A qualitative analysis of the strain measured along the tensile axis and mean displacements of the moving part and bolt head are performed from the DIC system focused on the face. The strain values presented in this study are normalised.

2.3 Acoustic emission

An acoustic emission method was used to register hits produced by the specimen during loading. Four acoustic emission sensors were fixed on the substrate around the joint’s area, on the side of the bolt head, so that hits could be localized.

So as to enable AE processing because of the higher number of recorded hits, an amplitude filter is applied. Only hits over 70 dB are kept for analysis.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS BASED ON DIC DATA

3.1 Global mechanical behaviour

Figure 3 shows the two load-displacement gap curves corresponding to the two different set-ups. All strength values are normalised with respect to the highest recorded value. Load and displacement gap experimental values for two specific stages are identified in Table 1. These stages correspond, on the one hand, to the highest load (F_{max}), and on the other hand, to the ultimate failure load (F_u).

Set-up		Load (normalised)	Displacement gap (mm)
With swivelled clamp	F_{max}	1	3.69
	F_u		
No swivelled clamp	F_{max}	0.98	1.06
	F_u	0.92	1.1

Table 1: Experimental data of load and displacement gap obtained from both set-ups.

The highest load (F_{max}) is comparable for both set-ups. However the ultimate failure displacement is sharply higher for the set-up with swivelled clamp compared to the constrained specimen (*i.e.* no swivelled clamp).

Figure 3: Load - Displacement gap curves corresponding to the two different set-ups and identification of the four steps.

Table 2 shows the measured tangent stiffness ratio observed at different test stages. K1 stiffness fits in the starting stiffness of the joint. K2 stiffness is only calculated for the test with the fix/swivel clamps. K2 corresponds to the second loading after the unloading. Then K3 stiffness is calculated from the second linear portion of the load-displacement gap curve.

Set-up	$K1(\text{with swivelled clamp}) / K1(\text{no swivelled clamp})$	$K2/K1$	$K3/K1$
With swivelled clamp	0.96	0.99	0.24
No swivelled clamp		-	0.36

Table 2: Tangent stiffness ratio measured at three different test stages.

After unloading, the stiffness of the specimen is unchanged from the beginning of the test. K2 is similar to K1 (see $K2/K1$ in Table 2). So the mechanical integrity of the assembly is maintained. Furthermore the K1 stiffness is almost the same for both set-ups (see $K1/K1$ in Table 2). The boundary conditions do not affect the starting stiffness of the sample.

The impact of the boundary conditions can be seen in looking at the K3 stiffness. The configuration without swivelled clamp significantly increases the stiffness of the assembly compared to the configuration with swivelled clamp.

Overall and regardless of which boundary conditions was applied, the load-displacement gap curves show four steps in the mechanical behaviour of the assembly (Figure 3):

- The first step is characterized by a linear section;
- In the second step, the displacement gap is significant. An knee point can be seen on the load-displacement gap curve;
- In the third step, a second linear section is observed;
- In the fourth and last step, there is varying gap displacement depending on the boundary conditions. The final fracture of the assembly concludes this step.

3.2 Step by step identification of the mechanical behaviour

During the first step, the mean longitudinal displacements of the “fixed” and “moving” plates are almost the same, which results in a very low displacement gap (Figure 4a). Furthermore, it was observed on the face of the sample that the bolt head has the same displacement as the “moving” part as illustrated on figure 4b. It can be seen that the displacement gap between the “moving” part and the

bolt head is close to zero from the beginning of the tests to a load of 0.15. Hence longitudinal forces existing between the bolt and the plates are very small. No strain concentration can be seen on the surface of the material. In this starting step, tensile forces are transmitted through the contact surface between both plates, and the bolt is not yet involved.

The end of this linear stage reaches a relative load of 0.09 for the set-up with swivelled clamp. By reaching a relative load of 0.11 for the set-up without swivelled clamp, the end of linearity corresponds to almost the same load.

a. Displacement gap, and mean displacements of the “moving” and “fixed” part during step 1 and 2 for the configuration with swivelled clamp.

b. Creation of the contact between the bolt head and the “moving” plate.

Figure 4: Investigation of steps 1 and 2.

To characterize the second step, the mean displacement of the “moving” and the “fixed” parts are investigated. Both displacements are illustrated in Figure 4a. It can be seen that the mean displacement of the “moving” part is much more significant than the one of the “fixed” part. Hence the CMC plates slip with respect to one another.

This slip of the plates can also be observed when the displacement gap between the “moving” part and the bolt head is investigated. As shown on Figure 4b, beyond a load of 0.15 for the configuration with swivelled clamp, mean longitudinal displacements of the bolt head and the one of the “moving” part are clearly different. At this load stage, the mean displacement of the bolt head is lower than the one of the “moving” part. Hence the longitudinal forces between the bolt and the plates are increased leading to a sharp increase in longitudinal strain is detected around the bolt head (see Figure 5a and Figure 5b).

The out-of-plane displacement fields indicate that from a load of 0.25, the bending of the bolt head is slightly different from the bending of the plate. The out-of-plane displacement fields are no more uniform. Load of 0.25 corresponds to the knee point of the load-displacement gap curve.

All these observations are similar for the configuration without the swivelled clamp.

Figure 5: Evolution of the longitudinal strain for the configuration with the swivelled clamp.

Unloading occurring at the end of the second step provides some important information to understand the mechanical behaviour of the joint.

Indeed after unloading, the “fixed” and “moving” plates do not recover their initial positions as it can be seen on Figure 3. Moreover the material has undergone large residual strain around the hole. At this step, strain values are similar to the values observed before unloading.

In spite of large local strain deformation on the material generated following the slip of the plates, structural integrity of the assembly is maintained as can be seen from K2 stiffness (Table 2).

In the first two steps the boundary conditions have no influence on the global mechanical behaviour of the joint. The two load-displacement gap curves are indeed close together, and K1 stiffness is identical to K2 stiffness (Table 2). At the beginning of the test, the joint owes its global stiffness to ceramic plates’ stiffness.

The third step can be displayed on the load-displacement curve by a second linear section (Figure 3). Mechanical behaviour of the joint is affected by the boundary conditions as reflected in K3 stiffness (Table 2).

At the beginning of this step, the sample is still loaded in the same shear plane as at the beginning of the test, because there is practically no incline of the bolt (around 1°) and both set-ups are affected in a similar way.

As a result of the contact between the plates and the bolt introduced during the second step, the main strain is and remains concentrated around the fixing hole. The upper half of the periphery is a compression part, whereas the lower half is under tension (Figure 5c).

During this step, the tensile forces are now passed on by all the components of the sample, *i.e.* contact zone between plates and bolt. The loss of stiffness (K3) could be explained by the initial bending of the assembly resulting in a gradually decrease of the contact area between the two CMC plates. The loss K3 stiffness is more important for the configuration with swivelled clamp due to the greater bending and therefore the reduction of the contact area between the two plates compared to the configuration without swivelled clamp.

For both set-ups, the fourth step leads to the fracture of the joint. However boundary conditions have a high influence on the damage occurring during this final step.

The stiffness of the clamping jaws has an impact on the plates and bolt final bending. Indeed in the case without the swivelled clamp, hence with the most rigid configuration, the body of the bolt has only rotated through 4° from its initial position at specimen break (Figure 6a). In the second case when the assembly has more mechanical flexibility (*i.e.* with swivelled clamp), the inclines of the screw reached 10° when the fracture happened (Figure 6b). The increase of the bending of the assembly is enhanced by the flexibility provided by the swivelled clamp.

Figure 6: Comparison of tilted positions of the body of the bolt before rupture for both configurations: (a) without swivelled clamp and (b) with swivelled clamp.

Beyond a load of 0.84 for the configuration with the swivelled clamp, a wide area on top of the fixing hole was loaded in compression (Figure 7a). This huge deformation of the material leads to a local and gradual uplift of the CMC. This phenomenon can easily be observable at the end of the test (Figure 7b).

Regarding the configuration without swivelled clamp, only the area around the fixing hole is concerned by major deformations. Although the measured deformation under compression is higher, the strain concentration remains localized around the hole. No uplift can be seen at the surface of the material.

a. Longitudinal strain based on DIC measurements at 0.84 of F_{max}

b. Observable deflection at the end of the test

Figure 7: Highlighted deflection on top of the fixing hole for the configuration with swivelled clamp.

4 ACOUSTIC EMISSION DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Global data analysis

The acoustic analysis allowed to highlight significant steps in the damage process of the assembly. A quantitative analysis is investigated. For this first approach, three parameters are used: absolute energy, hits and events. For both configurations, these descriptors are collected according to the time,

and then related to the force level. So as to compare the three evolving parameters, they are normalized.

The analysis looks for significant changes in slope of the three above mentioned parameters.

It can be observed on figure 8 that hits and events evolve in a similar manner. These two parameters give the same information, so only the events are retained afterwards.

The changes in slope are particularly abrupt for the evolution of the absolute energy. The energy increases very strongly for loadings from 0.12 to 0.33 for the most rigid set-up (Figure 8a). For the configuration with swivelled clamp, two large increases are observed. The first one happens for loadings from 0.12 to 0.37, and the second one from 0.81 to 0.9 (Figure 8b). These moments correspond respectively to the bending of the sample, and to the significant degradation of the material on top of the fixing hole.

For both configurations, the final rupture of the sample is announced by a sharp increase for acoustic activity in both terms of energy and number of events.

A few events are recorded during unloading and then loading performed during the test with swivelled clamp. Figure 8b shows that the acoustic emission recovery is actually resumed from a load of 0.44 corresponding to the load previously reached before the unloading.

This first acoustic approach allows to distinguish different steps in the life of the assembly, and is in good agreement with conclusions based on DIC measurements.

Figure 8: Evolution of cumulative absolute energy, event and hit according to the time for both configurations: (a) without swivelled clamp and (b) with swivelled clamp.

4.2 Cluster analysis

Clustering of acoustic signals collected during tensile tests is performed using unsupervised k-mean algorithm. As descriptors absolute energy, amplitude, count to peak, risetime and duration are taken into account for classification, and acoustic signals are clustered into four classes defined by number and colours as presented in Table 3.

	Blue class n°1	Red class n°2	Green class n°3	Purple class n°4
With swivelled clamp	95.9 %	3.7 %	0.3 %	0.1 %
No swivelled clamp	92.7 %	6.8 %	0.2 %	0.2 %

Table 3: Portion of hits included into each class.

Figure 9: Load-Time curve corresponding to the hits of each cluster for both configurations: with swivelled clamp (left) and without swivelled clamp (right).

Figure 10: Discrimination of the four acoustic clusters plotting count to peak versus absolute energy for the configuration with swiveled clamp.

The blue class n°1 confirms the high acoustic emissivity of CMC materials, because signals qualified for this class are present in large numbers (>90%) (Table 3) from the beginning to the end of the tensile tests as it can be seen on figure 9. The following analysis will not focus on this class, since its average amplitude (76 dB), absolute energy and count to peak are very low (see Figure 10).

The three other classes (red, green and purple classes) have interesting properties (Figure 9 and Figure 10) discussed below.

The red class n°2 is characterized by signals with high average amplitude (91 dB) and low absolute energy and count to peak. It first appeared for a load of 0.09 for the configuration with swiveled clamp and for a load of 0.11 in the case without swiveled clamp, which corresponding to the end of linearity measured on the load/displacement gap curve. Moreover some hits were recorded during unloading. Then the acoustic emission recovery is effective from a load of 0.44 thus coinciding with the load reached before the unloading.

The green class n°3 has the highest average amplitude (99 dB). All signals included in this class appear when the two plates were slipping for loadings from 0.1 to 0.35 for both configurations. Hits belonging to the green cluster have a low count to peak but a high absolute energy. The red and green classes are linked, because they appear at the same time. This moment corresponds to the second step, where the plates are slipping, hence rubbing with respect to one another.

The purple cluster n°4 is different from other classes with a high count to peak and a low absolute energy (Figure 10). There are very few hits allocated to this cluster (<0.2%) (see Table 3), and they only occur during loss of load and at final rupture (Figure 9). The emergence of this cluster reveals a huge damage of the sample including fibre rupture.

Three of the acoustic clusters previously mentioned are particularly interesting, and thus could be assigned to major macroscopic phenomena. The first one, the red cluster, appearing during a significant displacement gap evolution of both plates is indicative of matrix damage. The second one, the green cluster, highlights surface friction arising from the contact between the two CMC plates. These first two classes are strongly linked, explaining their simultaneous appearance. During the third step, the contact area between the two CMC plates gradually decreases due to the bending of the assembly. The reduced contact area must explain the decrease in the number of hits belonging to the green cluster attributed to the friction, contrary to matrix damage which is propagating.

And finally the third cluster, the purple one, collects hits representative of material degradation mechanisms including fibre rupture.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This experimental study allowed to understand the mechanical behaviour of Ceramic Matrix Composite assemblies but also to identify the damage process related to such structures. Experimental results demonstrated good agreement between DIC and AE.

Measurements from stereo Digital Image Correlation have highlighted the presence of four different stages in the mechanical behaviour of the assembly.

The acoustic emission analysis proposed in this study was used first to validate the existence of the steps identified with DIC analysis, and then to highlight four clusters, three of them being assigned to major macroscopic phenomena within matrix damage, friction and fibre rupture.

All these conclusions are aimed at establishing a dialog between experimental and numerical data so as to be able to implement new numerical models considering behaviour of assemblies of CMC (Bouillon *and al.* [7]).

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REFERENCES

- [1] T. Dang Hoang, C. Herbelot and A. Imad, Rupture and damage mechanism analysis of a bolted assembly using coupling techniques between A.E. and D.I.C., *Engineering Structures*, Vol. 32, pp. 2793-2803, 2010.
- [2] Y. Xia and T. Ishikawa, Bearing strength and failure behavior of bolted composite joints (part I: Experimental investigation), *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 65, pp. 1022-1031, 2005.
- [3] G. Li, X. Wu, C. Zhang and H. Hu, Theoretical simulation and experimental verification of C/SiC joints with pins or bolts, *Materials & Design*, Vol. 53, pp. 1071-1076, 2014.
- [4] G. Li, Y. Zhang, C. Zhang, H. Hu, S. Chen and Z. Zhang, Design, preparation and properties of online-joints of C/SiC–C/SiC with pins, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, Vol. 48, pp. 134-139, 2013.
- [5] N. Tableau, K. Khellil, Z. Aboura and L. Marcin, Caractérisation du cisaillement inter et intra laminaire d'un matériau CMC, *Proceedings of the 18th Journées Nationales sur les Composites*, Nantes, France, 2013.
- [6] N. Tableau, K. Khellil, Z. Aboura, P. Feissel, F. Bouillon and L. Marcin, Experimental investigation of the in plane and trough thickness shear damages on interlock woven CMC using multi-instrumented torsional tests, *Proceedings of the 16th European Conference on Composite Materials*, Sevilla, Spain, 2014.
- [7] T. Vandellos, F. Bouillon, A. Candéau, B. Legin, E. Voland, F. Laurin and Z. Aboura, Sizing of bolted junctions for 3D-woven ceramic matrix composites structures using ONERA damage model and comparisons with multi-instrumented tests, *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Composite Materials*, Copenhagen, Denmark, July 19-24, 2015.